

Council on Library Resources, Inc.

Twenty-Sixth Annual Report/1982

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Council on Library Resources, Inc.
1785 Massachusetts Ave., N.W.
Washington, D.C. 20036
1982

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The scholar at his book-wheel is a reproduction of an engraving in Agostino Ramelli's *Le diverse et artificiose machine* . . . Paris, 1588. It first appeared in the Council's third annual report, with the following explanation: "the picture symbolizes the interest of the Council on Library Resources in both the content of books and the mechanics of library service." The engraving has appeared in each annual report since that time.

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3. Mr. Cole was elected to succeed Mr. Wells at the November 1981 annual meeting.

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Preface

This *26th Annual Report* of the Council on Library Resources tests a new format. Currently active grants and contracts are grouped in major program categories and only briefly described, thus reducing substantially the bulk (and hence the cost) of the report while maintaining the record of CLR activity. Financial statements also are included. Individuals wishing additional information about the scope and current status of any grant are encouraged to write to the Council.

To supplement this report, special publications on topics of interest to the library and scholarly communities will, in the future, be prepared and distributed widely. Such topical reports, future *Annual Reports*, and issues of *CLR Recent Developments* should, when taken together, maintain and even improve understanding of CLR directions among librarians and, it is hoped, among those they serve.

One event of the past year, recorded only as part of the title page of this report, deserves special mention here. In June, 1982, the Council's offices moved from One Dupont Circle to 1785 Massachusetts Avenue. The move was the second major location change in the Council's history, and the fourth actual move. The building on Massachusetts Avenue is the headquarters of the National Trust for Historic Preservation.

Introduction

The Preface of CLR's *25th Annual Report* described the work of a special committee of the Board of Directors that had been asked to consider ways the Council might be most useful to the library and scholarly communities during the decade ahead.¹ We noted then that before the end of the twenty-sixth year, the CLR program would be adjusted to reflect the observations and recommendations incorporated in the report of the committee and subsequent Board discussions. This Introduction provides some sense of the changes under way.

The labels attached to CLR's programs are neither surprising nor exceptional. If anything, they suggest continuity of effort in areas of obvious importance. There are, however, several important factors that promise to make the years ahead very different from those of the past. First is the manner of CLR operations. Perhaps more consistently than in earlier years, program staff members are actively involved in both planning and monitoring many CLR-funded projects. The present dynamic character of librarianship and related professions, and the need to encourage cooperation among the growing number of participants involved in an enterprise of increasing complexity suggest that purposeful coordination is required to help assure that the limited funds available are used to maximum effect. To this end, the Council's small staff works hard to make useful information readily available to individuals involved in CLR-funded projects and to others working in closely related areas.

A second change that will, over time, affect CLR operations is the narrowing in scope of each program. In large part, this is necessary if limited resources are to be concentrated on specific objectives. It also reflects the realities of a fundamen-

¹Members of the committee are listed on page 31.

tal change in CLR funding, which has shifted from general support from a single source to specifically targeted funds from many foundations.

Finally, and most important by far, is a change in emphasis from essentially "library centered" projects to the external relationships that more and more will characterize the library future. Greater diversity in the needs and expectations of library users, further expansion of information sources and services beyond libraries and traditional book and journal publishing, an increasingly complex economic base, and the fundamental changes implicit in text storage, communications and computer technologies will alter the setting in which libraries work. While the program areas that have been identified for the future are linked to those of the past, the relationships between libraries and other components of our system of scholarly communication have now become a matter of primary importance.

With this backdrop, we can note and comment briefly on the program areas that will equally claim CLR attention during the years immediately ahead.

The national aspects of collection development and preservation.

There are encouraging signs that libraries are beginning to act as if they believe the oft-repeated assertion that, at least for general research libraries, the myth of self-sufficiency is finally dead. There are also signs that the implications of interdependency are not yet fully acknowledged, possibly because system capabilities are still no match for user needs. The archival and the information service roles of libraries, which are quite different, are not yet fully defined for our time, and the best means to meet the responsibilities inherent in each are not yet worked out. The collective responsibilities of the community of libraries (and we assert that they exist) are even less well understood. It seems an inescapable conclusion that new capabilities for joint action must be established by libraries to meet their collective responsibilities for building and preserving research collections and to accomplish their own institutional goals.

Bibliographic service for library users. Bibliographic functions, and especially computerized bibliographic services, have dominated CLR activities almost from the beginning. Nearly 40 percent of all CLR grant funds have been used to support projects in this general category. A significant portion of the work done by American libraries in the last 15 to 20 years to develop computerized bibliographic systems, to plan and establish networks, to experiment with specialized computer applications, to develop standards, to establish and expand data bases, and even to train (directly and indirectly) large numbers of specialists, can be traced, at least in part, to CLR funding and staff assistance.

As a result of this work by many individuals and organizations, the country is well on the way to having comprehensive, accessible, high quality data bases, and the computerized systems for using them. Such systems have transformed the internal operations of many libraries, and they are improving access to published materials outside the holdings of each user's own principal library.

Work has progressed to the point where more effort now can be transferred from addressing operating requirements to meeting users' needs. Current work on online catalogs and subject access suggests new and fertile areas for study and action. Improved bibliographic products, the linking of independent systems on behalf of users, and the international extension of bibliographic services are among the matters that now require attention.

Access to documents and information. The actual delivery of documents or information elements depends first on their existence, and second, on accessible descriptive records that include locations. These elements—the collections and data bases themselves, the bibliographic services that serve as keys, and the access systems that link would-be users to needed items—are the substance of libraries, individually and collectively. The changing character of libraries and the environment in which they operate are forcing changes in each of these fundamental elements. In terms of collections, libraries are unavoidably becoming interdependent. Bibliographic services are growing increasingly sophisticated and more comprehensive. Access changes are less evident, but the sheer quantity of publications, new ways to store and distribute information, and expanding, increasingly specialized user expectations are all forces pressing for change in the long established means of access, which is for most people still a personal visit to the local library, supplemented on rare occasions by a cumbersome, but now improving interlibrary loan system.

In a sense, access to bibliographic data and a growing commitment to cooperative collecting have created the new library frontier—improving the means of access to items and information. There is clearly no single or “right” path to success. The key seems to be to help promote development of new ways of access to be used by libraries and their users as necessary. Access to “items” is almost certainly a matter of improving relationships among institutions, while access to “information” seems to be a challenge for technology. As with all other CLR interests, the Council can do little by itself. We plan during the next few years to concentrate much of our effort and resources in this area and, as we have done in the past, “help the leaders lead.”

If progress in the three areas identified above is the key to future library performance, then attention to three additional topics seems essential to this progress.

Management. The general subject of library management has had an important place on the Council's agenda since 1970, and there seems every reason to continue this work. The report of the CLR special committee emphasizes future problems of libraries, operating as they will be in a setting marked by new and diverse information services offered in a market which otherwise distributes and prices its services in keeping with user demand. The set of topics needing attention that stem from this basic enigma are essentially problems of management. Many if not most of them are related to the costs and funding of libraries, and it is on this topic that the management program will focus. An attempt will be made

to probe alternative routes to the overriding goal of supporting scholarship and research and the more general information needs of the public. The principal assets of libraries, in addition to collections and buildings, are the skills of their staffs, their operating funds, and the service potential of their organized affiliations. Better ways of using these assets need to be discovered and employed if service obligations, both short and long term, are to be met in a fiscally responsible way.

Technology. Technology *per se* has been designated a primary topic for CLR attention simply because computers, communication systems, and text storage methods—together the heart of the technical revolution so far as library and information services are concerned—promise to transform the support system for research, scholarship, and teaching during the decade ahead. But these technologies are, in the final analysis, means to an established set of ends, and it follows that libraries and the institutions of which they are a part need to make a special effort to use the methods wisely and to greatest effect. Because technology affects the process it serves and because the application of technology to information systems inevitably forces change in economic and organizational patterns, it seems essential that this subject be an integral part of the Council's primary program. The key question for CLR attention is not whether these technologies will be used but rather how they can be used most effectively in an intellectually and financially responsible way.

Professional education. CLR has, for many years, sought ways to help individual librarians develop their skills and expand their professional horizons. Convinced that the library profession is more demanding than ever before, CLR is assisting library educators and professional leaders to consider all aspects of professional education. The aim is to help make certain that those who will guide the library transformation projected for the future and who will be responsible for operating the new information services will be up to their tasks, in terms of abilities and understanding. Only distinctive professional leadership and exceptional talents can turn careful planning, reasonable funding, and technological capabilities into the library and information services that are essential to our nation. The subject of the profession itself is the last listed here, but it is the base on which all else rests.

This overview of the work ahead gives some idea of CLR's sense of its own future. The Council, by itself, can accomplish nothing. We will, as we have from the beginning, rely on help from many people in many places to accomplish at least a few of the items that our friends and advisors tell us are on the profession's current agenda.

It seems especially appropriate, as we reflect on future directions, to take note of the importance of private foundations to CLR. Put precisely, without the support of many private foundations, there would be no Council on Library Resources.

For the first twenty of our twenty-six years, the Ford Foundation funded the Council, and in effect, CLR was the Ford Foundation's library program. The extent and persistence of Ford's attention to library concerns is an exceptional example of foundation perception and leadership. Even more remarkable is the fact that, during the last six years, a growing number of foundations have demonstrated a willingness to support not only CLR, but the cause of libraries in general. Many of their representatives have taken an active part in forming and extending a deeper understanding of the issues related to collecting, preserving, organizing and making accessible recorded information in all subjects and formats. This set of tasks is, in a real sense, at the heart of civilization and essential to public progress, which perhaps explains foundation interest and support.

Richard Sullivan, Vice President, Finance, and Treasurer of the Carnegie Corporation and, until his death in the spring of 1982, the prime mover and guiding spirit of an informal foundation library committee, once underscored for his colleagues the fact that libraries didn't fit the mold of many other foundation projects in that they seemed to need consistent help over an extended period of time if they were to be recast successfully, in ways that would both "preserve and extend." This postscript acknowledges Dick's personal attention to our cause, as well as the continuing interest of many others in the foundation world who not only provide funds, but, equally important, help us all as we try to focus our efforts on primary targets and assist us in developing affiliations with the scholarly, academic, governmental and commercial worlds that are essential to ultimate success.

Warren J. Haas

Bibliographic Services

The Council's **Bibliographic Service Development Program (BSDP)** entered its fourth year in November, 1981.¹ Focused on helping to assure access to a comprehensive set of bibliographic record data bases, assisting the development of required products from those data bases, and controlling costs of bibliographic processes in libraries, BSDP activities continue on several fronts. During the year substantial progress was made in a number of program areas, especially in projects to evaluate online public access catalogs and to link bibliographic computer systems. Preparatory work for another program area, subject access, also has begun.

The activities related to linking computer systems deserve special comment. After the possibilities for building a single national bibliographic record data base were explored during the early stages of the BSDP, it became evident that while such a data base was not economically feasible, the same effect could be gained by linking the existing major bibliographic data bases. In order to build links that would allow any given system to be accessed by users of other computer systems, however, a number of technical problems had to be solved. The kinds of data to be transmitted between systems had to be defined, and the technical capabilities needed to accomplish the task required development and standardization, and this work is under way in several BSDP projects. These projects will have substantial impact on libraries, because when the developmental work is completed, it will be possible to use the system links for purposes other than communicating bibliographic records—for example, interlibrary loan requests, messages, and memos. Moreover, computing applications of all kinds may be affected by the development of the telecommunication protocols described below.

During fiscal 1982, over 40 BSDP grants were active, and funding amounting to nearly \$2 million was administered through the program. As a guide to the wide-ranging efforts to improve bibliographic services, the projects are described below under broad, topical headings.

¹Members of BSDP committees are listed on pages 31 and 32.

Standards And Guides

Recognizing the need for consistent, dependable methods of accomplishing agreed-on tasks, the BSDP has devoted much effort to helping develop codes, protocols, and standards. Uniform methods are required to facilitate nearly every aspect of bibliographic record sharing. The contents of book and serial catalog records, records for nonbook materials, communication formats, and the means of receiving and communicating information all have been subjects for attention during the past four years. This year, some BSDP participants have been involved in a complex project to develop sets of rules, or *protocols*, that govern how information is transmitted from one computer to another.

Standard Network Interconnection (SNI)

The Research Libraries Group (RLG), the Washington Library Network (WLN), and the Library of Congress (LC), are developing a standard means of linking computer systems. OCLC, Inc. also is involved in this work in an advisory and support capacity. The project will produce a set of telecommunication protocols that can be used to enable one computer system to communicate with another. The work builds on existing telecommunication standards—the Reference Model for Open Systems Interconnection of the American National Standards Institute and the International Standards Organization. The model is designed in seven layers, and because the lower levels already have been developed, the RLG/WLN/LC portion of the work is directed toward levels 4, 5, and 6. A description of the proposed network, titled “Network Topology Document,” has been completed.

Application Level Protocol

The seventh and final layer of the model, called the *Application Level Protocol*, is being developed at Northwestern University. James Aagaard of the Library’s Information Systems Development Office is cooperating with participants in the Standard Network Interconnection project to assure compatibility of this work with the lower level protocols. In June, 1982, a supplementary grant was made to assist coordination of the protocol development with similar activities in Canada.

American National Standards Committee Z-39

The Council has assisted the work of Committee Z-39, a part of the American National Standards Institute (ANSI), since 1961. Although CLR no longer provides general support funding, grants have been given for work on specific projects. The current BSDP support for Committee Z-39 is intended to assist progress on standards related to holdings information in bibliographic records, and telecommunication protocols. CLR funding also is provided for work on standards related to book paper quality.

Character Sets

Although much work on converting bibliographic records to machine-readable form already has been accomplished, records in non-Roman foreign languages

cannot as yet be included in bibliographic data bases. These languages present particular difficulty because standard character sets and coordination with requirements for transliteration need to be established before bibliographic control of the publications can be addressed. International planning for standards in this area currently is in progress by working groups sponsored by the International Standards Organization (ISO). In 1981, the BSDP provided funds for a staff member from the Library of Congress Network Development Office to attend a Paris meeting of the ISO's Working Group on Character Sets.

Non-Roman Character Sets

OCLC, Inc. received a CLR grant in 1978 to develop a non-Roman character set capability for computerized input, storage, processing, and display of bibliographic information. For organizational and economic reasons, OCLC has withdrawn from this project.

Serials Cancellation

A 1981 grant went to the Pittsburgh Regional Library Center to develop a prototype system for recording and communicating subscription cancellation decisions via an online union list. The project is scheduled to be completed in late 1982.

Linking Bibliographic Data Bases: The Linked Systems Project

The Linked Systems Project (LSP), formerly called the Linked Authority Systems Project (LASP), is central to the goals of the BSDP. The project goal is to develop, coordinate, and link the bibliographic and computer systems of three organizations: the Washington Library Network, the Research Libraries Group, Inc., and the Library of Congress, so that they can exchange bibliographic records and other information. In effect, these links will provide the technical environment required for a national bibliographic record service.²

This large project involves several different tasks. One group is developing computer-to-computer protocols (see p. 14), as part of the technical elaboration needed to link computer systems. The technical requirements involve standards development, which has been described above, under "Standards and Guides."

A second group is designing software to translate the language of individual computer systems into the language of the telecommunication link. This group also is planning to test the link through the exchange of authority records, using the work of the Task Force on a Name Authority File Service (see below).

During the first two phases of the LSP, participants conducted an assessment of the feasibility of linking systems, and defined a plan for accomplishing the work. RLG and WLN received assistance for their work in making necessary changes in their authorities systems to allow computer exchange of that information. Also, planning for the hardware and software required to achieve the link was carried

²For a detailed list of participants in this project, see pages 32-33.

on, and the telecommunication system itself was the subject of extensive analysis.

Two reports submitted to the Council describe some of the work carried on during these first phases. The Authorities Group submitted "LASP Functional Specifications: Intersystem Component" (March, 1981), which contains the specifications for the search and response, file maintenance and message functions of the linked systems. The Telecommunications Group completed "Protocol Evaluation, Survey of Network Offerings, Traffic Estimates and Assessment of Investment in Linkage" (March, 1981.).

Task Force on a Name Authority File Service (NAFS)

While the work of the Authorities and Telecommunications Groups progressed, the Council's Task Force on a Name Authority File Service (NAFS) was studying the requirements for operating the planned Service.³ In April, 1981, the Task Force completed its "Requirements Statement for a Name Authority File Service," and circulated it for comment from the library community. During late 1981 and early 1982 the group revised the document, and developed guidelines for Service operation and for the selection of contributing institutions. NAFS will be operated by the Library of Congress.

The Authorities Group has incorporated the requirements listed by the Task Force into its "LSP External Design: Intersystem Component" (February, 1982). The document contains detailed specifications for the software required to translate commands from each system into the language of the telecommunications link and back again into system language. This synthesis of LSP and NAFS work will enable LSP participants to exchange authority records as the first use of the computer system links.

Bibliographic Products

During the late seventies and early eighties, two separate developments have come together to provide a new means of accessing bibliographic information. One of these is the development of telecommunications that support widespread access to computerized data bases. The second is specific to libraries: the construction of large machine-readable data bases of bibliographic records. Bibliographic record data bases grew rapidly during the seventies, and many of them are now available to library users in the form of online public access catalogs (OPACs). However, even though a number of systems are in use, many questions about the online catalogs themselves and about how they are used by both librarians and users have not been answered. To address some of these questions, the BSDP has funded a set of online catalog evaluation studies.

Online Public Access Catalog (OPAC) Evaluation

Early in 1981, six groups began a two-year project to evaluate online public access catalogs nationwide. Current participants in the project are J. Matthews & Associates, the Online Computer Library Center (OCLC, Inc.), the Research

³Members of the Task Force are listed on page 31.

Libraries Group (RLG), the University of California, Division of Library Automation, and the Library of Congress.⁴ Due to circumstances beyond its control the University of Toronto Library Automation Systems (UTLAS), which had planned to participate, had to withdraw from the project.

During the first phase of the project, participants designed and tested questionnaires and other evaluation tools required for data collection. Northwestern University Library, Stanford University Library, and Dartmouth College Library received assistance to cover their participation in these preliminary planning activities, as well as in data collection efforts. OCLC, Inc. also received funding to support training activities for data collection personnel and interviewers.

The main data collection took place during April and May, 1982. The University of California, Division of Library Automation, with the aid of another BSDP grant, has undertaken the machine analysis of data collected by all participants in the project. A major report based on project research already has been published: Charles Hildreth's *Online Public Access Catalogs: The User Interface* (Dublin, Ohio, 1982). Early results of the data collection also have influenced another BSDP initiative: the investigation of subject access questions.

Subject Authority Structure

The BSDP's examination of problems relating to subject access to materials in research libraries began last year when Carol Mandel and Judith Herschman produced a paper titled "Subject Access in the Online Catalog." The paper provides an overview of research in the area, and describes some alternatives for improving subject access. Early results from the OPAC study substantiate the need to pursue research on subject access: most card catalog use studies show that only about one-fifth of the initial searches are by subject, but the OPAC users begin nearly two-thirds of their efforts with a subject search. This finding reinforced the decision to devote BSDP attention to subject access needs, especially in online systems.

In June, 1982, the BSDP organized a meeting of 23 specialists in the area of subject access to discuss current knowledge about the topic, and recommend ways to improve existing systems. Participants specified a number of changes and improvements that would require both short- and long-term projects. The draft recommendations currently are being reviewed by the group.

Subject Headings

The Council has contracted with Pauline Atherton Cochrane to develop a plan to enhance the cross reference structure of the *Library of Congress Subject Headings* (LCSH). A progress report titled "Current Cross Reference Practice in LCSH—Its Impact on Online Searching" has been received. The project is scheduled to be completed in October, 1982.

⁴For a detailed list of participants in the project, see page 32.

Bibliographic Records on Microcomputers

Victor Rosenberg, University of Michigan School of Library Science, has received a BSDP grant to produce computer programs to extract and reformat bibliographic records. The records will come from shared cataloging service data bases, such as OCLC and the Research Libraries Information Network (RLIN).

MARC Record Analysis

In June, 1982, the Council received *MARC Database Statistics: An Aid to BSDP Participants*, the final report on a project to compile statistics on the MARC data base. Martha Williams, University of Illinois Coordinated Science Laboratory, investigated changes in record length, field tag occurrences, and field lengths for records produced during the period 1973-1981. She also has analyzed relationships among selected fields within the records.

AACR-II Catalog Headings

An assessment of the differences in Anglo-American Cataloging Rules (AACR-II) applications in four national libraries is being conducted by C. Donald Cook, University of Toronto. Cook's study focuses on unplanned variations in headings for names of persons and corporate bodies established by the National Library of Australia, the National Library of Canada, the British Library, and the Library of Congress.

Access To Bibliographic Data

New ways of accessing bibliographic data and publications are appearing because the advent of machine-readable data bases has made such alternatives possible. To address questions related to access, the BSDP has funded projects to evaluate the use of data bases and the addition of new capabilities for locating and delivering information.

Network Advisory Committee

The BSDP provided support for three meetings of the Network Advisory Committee to the Library of Congress during the past year. The meetings focused on resource sharing and on the need to improve the delivery of information as a direct response to improved identification of locations through online bibliographic data bases.

Cataloging in Publication Program

In 1980, the Council provided funds to the Cataloging in Publication Division of the Library of Congress for an evaluation of the program's effectiveness and impact. The report on the evaluation, titled *CIP Survey Final Report*, was received in May, 1982. Nearly 2,400 libraries of all types—school, public, special, college, and university—were included in the survey, and over 70% (1,657) responded. A majority of the respondents use CIP data as the basis for their catalog records, and most librarians have a favorable opinion of the program because it

enables them to search, process and catalog books faster. The report concludes with recommendations for future CIP activities based on the survey results.

Association of Research Libraries Microform Project

The Association of Research Libraries (ARL) received a BSDP grant in March, 1981, for activities intended to help improve bibliographic access to the content of microform collections. During the first year of the two-year project, a survey was conducted to obtain information on libraries' current cataloging efforts, existing catalog records, and other related activities.

Machine-Readable Humanities Texts

BSDP funds support Rutgers University's project to build an international inventory of machine-readable texts in the humanities. Data on existing texts will be received through responses to a questionnaire, and the information will be prepared for subsequent input as a specific data base in the Research Libraries Information Network (RLIN). A microfiche catalog also will be produced.

Conversion Of Serials (CONSER)

The Conversion of Serials (CONSER) project is a cooperative effort among libraries to build a data base of bibliographic records for serial publications. In the past, the Council has provided funding to support CONSER management and for projects related to building the data base. Currently, several CONSER-related projects are receiving support.

Theological Journals

The Boston Theological Institute is adding unique titles in religion and theology to the CONSER data base. CLR has provided partial support for this project, and in fiscal 1982 made a supplemental grant to help defray telecommunications costs incident to the input of additional entries. The extra entries were required because of added cataloging requirements.

Abstracting and Indexing Coverage

The BSDP provided funds to support travel costs for participants in an August, 1981, Association of Research Libraries—National Federation of Abstracting and Indexing Services meeting to develop a detailed operational plan for adding information to the CONSER data base. The group has developed a proposal to input information on which indexing and abstracting services include titles in the CONSER data base. The information would be added to the records for each title covered.

Telecommunication Costs

The Council continues to support U.S. telecommunication costs for CONSER participation by the National Library of Canada.

Professional Education, Training, And Research

The Council's **Professional Education and Training for Research Librarianship (PETREL)** program entered its second year in fiscal 1982. Four major projects, including three professional education programs and a Frontiers Conference, have been funded under the program. Other activities aimed at improving education and training and providing opportunities for professional growth have also received support. In the PETREL program, as in other CLR programs, the assistance of library educators, library and university administrators and others continues to be important in helping establish program directions.

In June, 1982, the PETREL Advisory Committee invited library school deans, library directors and personnel officers to a two-day meeting to discuss the place of internships in professional education, and to consider other topics pertaining to careers in librarianship.¹ The Committee's aim was to assess both current program efforts and suggested new endeavors. The Council will distribute a program report on issues and priorities that will include the substance of the June discussions.

In addition to the PETREL grants, the Council has provided assistance for several other projects related to research and training. For example, the **Academic Library Management Intern Program**, which began in the mid-seventies, was reviewed during 1981. The program will resume during 1982/83 with the selection of the ninth group of interns.

Professional Education Programs

Basic Professional Education

In 1981, the University of Michigan School of Library Science was awarded a two-year grant of up to \$275,000 to recruit highly qualified graduates of liberal arts and sciences programs to the profession of research librarianship, and to develop a specialized curriculum in that area. The first class, composed of four students, is now halfway through the program, and a second six-member class will begin work in September, 1982. All the students are taking some courses in academic departments other than the School, and they will complete one-term

¹Members of the Committee are listed on page 33.

internships in cooperating research libraries. Graduates of the two-year program will receive the Master of Arts in Library Science. PETREL funding provided for this program is primarily for student aid.

Advanced Study in Library Management

A program to advance working professionals' knowledge of management theory and practice, and to prepare them for senior management positions in research libraries, has begun at the University of Chicago Graduate Library School. Chicago has received a two-year grant of up to \$250,000 for the program, which includes Business School and Library School course work, a management seminar, and an investigative internship. Six students have been recruited for the first-year program, and, on completion of their work, will receive a Certificate of Advanced Study in Library Management. PETREL support for this program provides tuition assistance and stipends.

Senior Fellows

The Graduate School of Library and Information Science at the University of California, Los Angeles, has received funding to operate a Senior Fellows Program for three years, beginning in August, 1982. The program is intended to provide individuals who have assumed major administrative responsibilities in libraries with an intensive educational experience to enhance their management skills, and to give them a chance to work with leading library educators. The program will include interdisciplinary coursework, a seminar on current library management issues, and individual research projects, all scheduled so that the administrators can participate without leaving their posts for any significant amount of time. The initial six-weeks' session will be followed by year-long individual research projects. During the year, the Fellows will meet several times to discuss their research.

Frontiers Conference

"Universities, Information Technology, and Academic Libraries: The Next Twenty Years" was the theme of the first frontiers conference. Funded by a \$90,000 grant from CLR, the five-day conference was hosted by the Graduate School of Library and Information Science, University of California, Los Angeles, in December, 1981. Forty-nine invited participants from libraries, library schools, university administration, and associations met to discuss predicted changes in academic institutions and the implications for research libraries.

The conference was intended to serve two purposes: first, it provided an extraordinary educational opportunity for a selected group of professionals both inside and outside librarianship; and second, it helped the profession identify the areas that require research and development assistance in the immediate future. Commissioned papers by university administrators provided information and questions for the discussions that took place in workshop sessions following the presentations. Another frontiers conference is planned for 1983.

Research Support

As the year ended, a new PETREL project was launched: research support for joint projects by faculty members and librarians. Those whose projects receive funding will be given small grants not exceeding \$3,000 each to cover the incremental costs of their research.

Education for Health Sciences Librarianship

The report of a PETREL-funded investigation into the Medical Library Association's role in educating health sciences librarians was issued in October, 1981. Titled *MLA's Role in the Educational Process for Health Sciences Librarians*, the report describes past MLA commitments and recommends future Association action in this area.

Faculty Development in Information Science

A project under way at C. W. Post Center, Long Island University, was extended to include the fall semester of 1981. The project goal is to prepare faculty members from C. W. Post, St. John's University, and Queens College to teach introductory information science courses. The new courses are to be integrated into the library school curriculum.

British Academic Library Research

Jovana J. Brown, Evergreen State College, has received a CLR grant to study the British Library Research and Development Department funding of academic library research in Great Britain. Her project focuses on trends and patterns in funding, and includes case studies of projects at several university research units.

Academic Library Management Intern Program

The Council's Academic Library Management Intern Program was suspended during fiscal 1982, pending its evaluation by CLR staff, program participants, and others. For the program review, the Council invited past interns and library directors who served as hosts to comment on aspects of their experience, especially their opinions about its lasting value. Their replies made it clear that both hosts and interns believe that the program provides a unique and important experience that enhances participants' career opportunities.

During the spring of 1982, the Council made preparations to select a 1983-1984 class of interns, and to resume the program.

Library Resources And Their Preservation

Helping to assure the availability of collections and information resources needed to support library use is the continuing focus of this area of the Council's programs. Preservation needs no longer require documentation, but finding effective and fiscally responsible methods for restoring, maintaining, and protecting collections is an ongoing concern. A special CLR committee has devoted two years to efforts to help librarians, publishers, and others evaluate more carefully the materials used in book manufacturing. The committee's goal is to prevent at least some future preservation problems.

Closely related to collection development and preservation is research on library use and users' requirements. Variations in needs according to fields of interest, current collecting patterns, and improved indexing and location services all are topics of concern in this area. CLR projects therefore cover a wide range of interests pertinent to the production and use of library resources, from the chemical composition of book paper to assistance for the production of reference books and aids to research.

Longevity in Book Paper and Bindings

The Council's **Committee on Production Guidelines for Book Longevity** continued its work in 1981-1982.¹ During the past year, the group has concentrated on evaluating materials and techniques used in book binding and assessing the current use of acid-free paper in the U.S. publishing community. A report on publishers' use of acid-free paper was completed for the committee. Near the end of the year, an interim report titled *Longevity in Book Binding* was issued. The Committee will produce a final report including its work on book paper and bindings, plus a summary of the survey of publishers, in the fall of 1982.

Use of Library Materials

Paul Metz, of the University Libraries, Virginia Polytechnic Institute and State University, has received funding for a thirteen-month study of the use of library

¹Members of the Committee are listed on page 35.

materials according to the status and disciplinary affiliation of library users. Metz is surveying both book and journal use habits according to department affiliation, within the University's almost completely centralized library system. Much of the data for the study is provided by records from the library's automated circulation system. This work is intended to extend earlier library use studies and to supplement bibliometric research on literature use.

Choice Periodical List

The Council's support for a regular column in *Choice* magazine began in 1975. The column provides evaluations of new periodicals and serials for college and university libraries.

British Library Resources

Robert B. Downs, of the University of Illinois, is the author of *British and Irish Library Resources: A Bibliographical Guide* (1981). This is the second edition of the *Guide*, which was first published in 1972. A 1979 CLR grant assisted Downs' travel to the British Isles to do the research for the book.

Leaders in Librarianship

Wayne Wiegand, University of Kentucky, is the coordinator of a three-year project to produce essays on 15 prominent academic library leaders who were active during the period 1925-1975. The *Journal of Academic Librarianship* has published several of the essays, and a book-length collection of all the contributions is currently in preparation.

Byzantine Bindings

Using materials in the collection of the Monastery of St. John, in Patmos, Greece, John L. Sharpe III of Duke University and Guy Petherbridge, a consultant, are gathering information on Byzantine bindings dating from the twelfth through the sixteenth centuries. Because little is known about Greek codicology, their research concentrates on collecting information about a selected group of manuscripts and constructing a profile of traditional features of Greek bookbinding.

Collection Assessment

Four member libraries of the Cooperative College Library Center, a cooperative processing unit based in Atlanta, are testing a collection assessment manual for small academic libraries. The manual was produced as part of an earlier CLR project. Atlanta College of Art, Dillard University, Tougaloo College and Tuskegee Institute are participating in the study, which is coordinated by the Office of Management Studies of the Association of Research Libraries. The ARL will make the manual generally available when it is completed.

Library Operations And Services

The Council maintains a strong interest in research library operations, including management, services, and economic matters. Past grants have helped individual libraries establish bibliographic instruction programs, improve communications with faculty, and experiment with ways to enhance the library's role in the teaching and learning process. Similarly, CLR has encouraged the study of topics related to library management, and recently provided funding to explore current issues related to the economics of research libraries.

Still another concern—and one that is receiving more and more of both librarians' and users' attention—is access to library resources. Bibliographic systems have improved rapidly during recent years—more rapidly than the ability to deliver information and materials to users. Locating needed materials and finding the fastest and most inexpensive ways to obtain them are problems that librarians have tried to solve through special agreements, local cooperation, and enhanced delivery and communication capabilities. However, the existing delivery systems need to be improved, and some of the underlying questions about access to materials have not been answered. In order to improve library services, it is important to know, for example, how the locations of materials relate to their use, what kind of subject access to bibliographic records is most satisfactory, and what methods of storing and delivering materials are most cost effective. These and other economic, legal, and operational questions require further exploration.

The Economics of Research Libraries

The Association of Research Libraries (ARL), in cooperation with the Research Libraries Group, Inc. (RLG), received CLR funding early in 1981 to explore questions related to research library economics and financing. On October 14, the two organizations sponsored a meeting on the topic in Washington, D.C. Eighteen university academic and administrative officers, library directors, economists and management specialists were invited to attend. Participants discussed libraries' current economic situation and approaches to solving financial problems, and they identified areas for attention in the context of expectations for the future. A report on the meeting, titled *The Economics and Financial Management of Research Libraries*, was issued in March, 1982.

Academic Library Program (ALP)

Since 1970, the Council has provided support for the Association of Research Libraries Office of Management Studies (OMS). Established to foster improvement in library management and fiscal practices, the OMS provides assistance to individual academic libraries and their staffs through self-study and planning programs, consultation, publications, and training assistance. In 1978, the Office consolidated its assisted self-study programs in the Academic Library Program, funded by the Council through a grant from the Carnegie Corporation of New York, and others. This funding, plus cost recovery from participants, has helped the OMS to develop and operate several types of self-study programs in which library staff members examine the current situation, review organizational needs, and recommend changes in library programs and activities.

In 1979, the Office implemented a Consultant Training Program. The program goal is to provide a selected number of librarians with the skills and experience to assist library self-study and training programs. During 1980 and 1981, forty librarians completed the intensive, two-week training workshop and began working with OMS staff on self-study and training projects. A third class of 17 trainees was selected in June, 1982.

Faculty—Library Communication

In April, 1981, the Council funded a meeting organized by the Association of Research Libraries and the American Association for the Advancement of the Humanities. The purpose of the meeting was to help find ways to improve communication between libraries and the scholarly community. One recommendation made by the participants was that faculty members receive more information regarding problems and issues faced by research libraries. Accordingly, the Council funded the experimental distribution of a bimonthly newsletter, *Library Issues*, to faculty at three institutions: the University of Colorado, the University of North Carolina, Chapel Hill, and Princeton University.

College Library Program

The College Library Program is jointly sponsored by the Council and the National Endowment for the Humanities. Now in its last two years of operation, the program has involved 35 college and university libraries in projects designed to enhance the library's role on campus. Participants have constructed their own programs, but most have used the funding to institute or improve bibliographic instruction and other course-related activities. During fiscal 1982, Ball State University, the University of Evansville, St. Olaf College, and Johnson C. Smith University submitted final reports on their project activities. The remaining participants are scheduled to complete the program by the end of 1983.

Bibliographic Instruction Workshops

CLR grants to Earlham College provided funding for the sixth and seventh Conferences on Bibliographic Instruction, held in April, 1982, and planned for spring, 1983, respectively. The funding supports faculty travel to the Con-

ferences, which are designed to bring faculty members and librarians together to discuss integrating library use into the curriculum.

Access to Materials in Storage

Late in 1981, the University of Michigan Library received a CLR grant to conduct a study of faculty attitudes toward locating and obtaining materials held in storage. Project researchers proposed improvements in the current system that include more frequent deliveries of stored materials and better bibliographic access via online data bases, with terminals located in three humanities departments: History, English, and American Studies. Project activities have been delayed because of staffing changes at the library, but work is expected to begin early in 1983.

Archives Self-Study and Review

The Society of American Archivists (SAA) is conducting a project to establish a self-study evaluation process for archival agencies. Six institutions tested the study process and the accompanying documentation during 1981, and project coordinators have revised the materials in preparation for final SAA approval and publication.

Association of American Universities (AAU)

Funded by the Carnegie Corporation, the Andrew W. Mellon Foundation, and the National Endowment for the Humanities, a cooperative CLR-AAU project began in 1981 when the two organizations sponsored a meeting of twelve university officials, librarians, and foundation executives to discuss major issues facing research libraries. Task forces were formed to address five specific topics: bibliographic data bases and access to bibliographic information; resource sharing; preservation; technological applications; and the profession of research librarianship. By early 1982, the task forces had finished their work, and plans were under way for advancing action on their findings and recommendations.¹

The Records of Government

Prompted by archivists' and scholars' concerns about the procedures and methods used to acquire, preserve, and make accessible government records, the Council invited representatives of a number of institutions and associations to a June, 1982 meeting to consider suitable ways to address those concerns. The group has endorsed a major effort to find solutions to problems that concern archives and their users, and funding is being sought to support the work of a planned committee on government records.

¹Members of the Steering Committee and Task Forces are listed on page 34.

International Programs

The Council's support for international activities is directed, for the most part, to projects similar to those described in other sections of this report. Helping remove barriers to the exchange of bibliographic information, encouraging development of standards to facilitate that exchange, and assisting other countries to adopt existing codes and guidelines are examples of such projects. Most of the CLR funding continues to be channeled through international organizations.

The Exxon Education Foundation provided two general support grants for CLR international programs in 1979 and 1980. A third grant from the Foundation was received in 1981.

Copyright and International Exchange of Bibliographic Data

The International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions (IFLA) received a CLR grant in 1979 to study copyright law and the implications for international exchange of machine-readable bibliographic data. In early 1982, King Research Inc. completed *The IFLA International Study of Copyright of Bibliographic Records in Machine Readable Form* for the Federation. The report recommends bilateral exchange agreements among national bibliographic agencies as the most feasible current mechanism for governing the exchange of machine-readable bibliographic data.

Library Materials for the Handicapped

The 1979 grant to IFLA also supported preparation of a study of specialized aspects of copyright law: *Copyright and Library Materials for the Handicapped*, by Françoise Hébert and Wanda Noël. Completed in 1981, the book was made ready for publication with the help of a 1982 CLR supplementary grant. IFLA also will use part of the funds to pursue the recommendations included in the study.

International Cataloging in Publication (CIP)

The IFLA International Office for Universal Bibliographic Control has organized an international meeting to consider the standards for and implementation of cataloging in publication programs. Publishers and librarians from countries that

have CIP programs, or plan to begin them, will attend the August, 1982 conference. A CLR grant supports preparation and distribution of preliminary studies, conference papers, and a final report.

International Standard Bibliographic Descriptions (ISBD)

IFLA's International Office for Universal Bibliographic Control is coordinating a review of those International Standard Bibliographic Descriptions that have been in use for five years. The purpose is to review rather than to revise the ISBD texts, and changes will be made only to improve their clarity and consistency. The CLR grant for the review also supports consultant assistance for developing countries attempting to establish national bibliographic structures. Consultant services will be provided by the director of the International Office for Universal Bibliographic Control to countries that request this assistance. Special attention will be given to advising on the preparation of new national bibliographies.

International Council on Archives (ICA)

Thomas Wadlow's *The Disposition of Government Records*, a records management manual for third world countries, was the subject of discussion at an international seminar organized by ICA and the National Archives of India. The Council provided support for the production of the manual, and in 1981, made an additional grant to ICA to test it at a regional seminar. Held in New Delhi, India, in October, 1981, the seminar also was sponsored by the Government of India. Archivists from India, Nepal, Pakistan, Malaysia, Sri Lanka, and Iraq attended the meeting. The proceedings have been published under the title: *Disposition of Government Records: Proceedings of the International Seminar*.

International Association of School Librarianship (IASL)

On the occasion of its tenth anniversary, the IASL received a small CLR grant to help expand its programs. The Association plans to expand its publications program, widen participation by representatives from developing countries in its annual conferences, and implement cooperative activities with other international organizations.

Dewey Decimal Classification – Arabic Edition

Forest Press, publisher of the Dewey Classification, is preparing an Arabic edition of Abridged Edition 11 of the schedules. In cooperation with the Arab League Educational, Cultural, and Scientific Organization (ALESCO), the press is attempting to assure effective Dewey coverage of Arab culture and to provide libraries in Arabic-speaking countries with a useful cataloging tool. The nearly complete text is currently under review.

Travel Grants

During fiscal 1982, several travel grants provided opportunities for professional activity that would otherwise be unavailable. IFLA received one such grant, to enable an Executive Board member to attend the UNESCO/IFLA Congress on the Universal Availability of Publications in Paris, in May, 1982. Two senior staff

members of the National Library of China (Beijing), Ms. Liu Guangwei, and Ms. Sun Peixin, received assistance for an intensive six-months' study and training period at the Library of Congress in 1982. Rutherford D. Rogers, chair of the Programme Management Committee of IFLA, received funding to attend meetings of the Committee. A report was received on the British Lending Library-United Kingdom Serials Group conference on resource sharing held in April, 1981. The Council supported the direct travel costs for a Library of Congress representative at the conference.

Program Committees, Task Forces, and Project Participants

CLR BOARD OF DIRECTORS

Ruth Davis, *CHAIR, CLR Board*
Robert O'Neil, *President, University of
Wisconsin*

SPECIAL COMMITTEE

Neil Rudenstine, *Provost, Princeton University*
Robert Vosper, *CLR Board*

BIBLIOGRAPHIC SERVICE DEVELOPMENT PROGRAM

Henriette Avram, *Library of Congress*
Rowland Brown, *OCLC, Inc.*
Joan Gotwals, *University of Pennsylvania*
James Govan, *University of North Carolina*
Carol Ishimoto, *Harvard University*

PROGRAM COMMITTEE

Frederick Kilgour, *OCLC, Inc.*
Edward Shaw, *Research Libraries Group, Inc.*
Roderick Swartz, *Washington State Library*

BIBLIOGRAPHIC SERVICE DEVELOPMENT PROGRAM

Raymond DeBuse, *Washington Library Network*
Joan Gotwals, *University of Pennsylvania*
Dorothy Gregor, *University of California,
Berkeley*

TASK FORCE ON A NAME AUTHORITY FILE SERVICE

Tina Kass, *Research Libraries Group, Inc.*
Lillian Kozuma, *National Library of Medicine*
Lucia Rather, *Library of Congress*
Patrick Mullin, *OCLC, Inc.*
Helen Schmierer, *University of Chicago*
Ruth Shipp, *Seattle Public Library*

**BIBLIOGRAPHIC
SERVICE DEVELOPMENT
PROGRAM**

**ONLINE PUBLIC ACCESS
CATALOG EVALUATION
STUDY PARTICIPANTS**

J. Matthews & Associates

Principal Investigator: Joseph Matthews

Libraries participating: Claremont Colleges, Evanston Public Library, Mankato State University, Mission College, Pikes Peak Library District, Stephen F. Austin State University, West Valley College.

The Library of Congress

Principal Investigator: Robert Zich

The Research Libraries Group (RLG)

Principal Investigator: Douglas Ferguson

Libraries participating: Dartmouth College, Northwestern University, Stanford University.

University of California, Division of Library Automation

Principal Investigators: Edwin Brownrigg
Gary Lawrence

Libraries participating: University of California Libraries at Berkeley, Davis, Irvine, Los Angeles, Riverside, San Diego, San Francisco, Santa Barbara, and Santa Cruz.

Online Computer Library Center (OCLC)

Principal Investigator: Neal Kaske

Libraries participating: Case Western Reserve University, Dallas Public Library, Iowa City Library, Ohio State University, Syracuse University, Ohio University, State Library of Ohio, University of Akron, University of Texas, Austin, University of Texas, Dallas.

**BIBLIOGRAPHIC
SERVICE DEVELOPMENT
PROGRAM**

**LINKED SYSTEMS
PROJECT**

Library of Congress

Principal Investigator and

Program Officer: Henriette Avram

Project Directors: Lucia Rather, Authorities

Sally McCallum, Authorities
and Telecommunications

Research Libraries Group, Inc.

Principal Investigator: Edward Shaw

Program Officer: John Heyeck

Project Directors: Tina Kass, Authorities
Wayne Davison,
Telecommunications*Washington Library Network*

Principal Investigator: Roderick Swartz

Program Officer: Robert Payne

Project Directors: Raymond DeBuse,
Authorities
Tom Brown,
Telecommunications**PROFESSIONAL
EDUCATION AND
TRAINING FOR RESEARCH
LIBRARIANSHIP**John McDonald, *Chair*
*University of Connecticut*Russell Bidlack
*University of Michigan*William Gerberding
*University of Washington***PROGRAM COMMITTEE**Margot McBurney
*Queens University*Rutherford Rogers
*Yale University*Robert Vosper
*University of California, Los Angeles***COUNCIL ON LIBRARY
RESOURCES AND
ASSOCIATION OF
AMERICAN UNIVERSITIES
PROJECT**Thomas Bartlett
*Association of American Universities*Richard Cyert
*Carnegie-Mellon University*Melvin Eggers
*Syracuse University***STEERING COMMITTEE**Hanna Gray
*University of Chicago*Warren Haas
*Council on Library Resources, Inc.*Sheldon Hackney
*University of Pennsylvania*Oscar Handlin
*Harvard University*Donald Koeppe
Princeton University

Robert Lumiansky
American Council of Learned Societies
 John McDonald
University of Connecticut
 David Stam
New York Public Library

CLR-AAU TASK FORCES

Bibliographic Systems

Hanna Gray, *University of Chicago, Chair*
 Patricia Battin, *Columbia University*
 Carol Ishimoto, *Harvard University*
 Wilfred Lancaster, *University of Illinois*
 Hans Rutimann, *Modern Language Association*
 William Welsh, *Library of Congress*

Professional Education and Training

John McDonald, *University of Connecticut, Chair*
 Margot McBurney, *Queens University*
 Russell Bidlack, *University of Michigan*
 William Gerberding, *University of Washington*
 Rutherford Rogers, *Yale University*
 Robert Vosper, *University of California, Los Angeles*

Preservation

David Stam, *New York Public Library, Chair*
 Herbert Bailey, *Princeton University Press*
 Margaret Child, *National Endowment for the Humanities*
 William Towner, *Newberry Library*
 Billy Frye, *University of Michigan*
 Jaroslav Pelikan, *Yale University*

Resource Sharing

Oscar Handlin, *Harvard University, Chair*
 James Govan, *University of North Carolina*
 Neil Harris, *University of Chicago*
 Richard Longaker, *Johns Hopkins University*
 Robert O'Neil, *University of Wisconsin*
 Clarence Ver Steeg, *Northwestern University*
 David Weber, *Stanford University*

Technology

Richard Cyert, *Carnegie-Mellon University, Chair*
 Ruth Davis, *The Pymatuning Group, Inc.*
 Otto Larsen, *National Science Foundation*
 Jay Lucker, *Massachusetts Institute of Technology*
 John McGowan, *Northwestern University*

**COMMITTEE ON
PRODUCTION GUIDELINES
FOR BOOK LONGEVITY**

Herbert Bailey, Jr. *Chair*
Princeton University Press
Frank Burke
*National Historical Publications and Records
Commission*
Warren Haas
Council on Library Resources, Inc.
Peter Mollman
World Book-Childcraft International, Inc.
Leonard Schlosser
Lindenmeyr Paper Corporation
David Stam
New York Public Library
Gay Walker
Yale University Library

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- Pearson, Dorothy A. "A Study of Technical Services Departments in Nine Major Academic Libraries." (CLR Fellow, 1978-1979)
- Pensyl, Mary E. "The Impact of the Growth of Online Bibliographic Services on User Demand, Collections, Reference Operations, and Professional Positions." (CLR Fellow, 1979-1980)
- Piternick, Anne B. "A Study of Support for Bibliographic Activity in the United States, Including Comparisons with the Situation in Canada." (CLR Fellow, 1979-1980)
- Robinson, Judith B. and Rao Aluri. "U.S. Government Produced Audiovisual Materials." *RQ* 21 (Fall, 1981) 23-26. (CLR Fellows, 1979-1980)
- Striedieck, Suzanne. "The Working Relationship Between Reference and Technical Services Departments." (CLR Fellow, 1979-1980)

Active Projects
Financial Statements

CLR-Supported Projects Active in Fiscal 1982 (unaudited)

GRANTS AND CONTRACTS

	FY 1982			
	Unpaid 6/30/81	Grants (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/82
American Association for the Advancement of the Humanities, Washington, D.C.				
AAAH/ARL sponsored meeting of research librarians and scholars	\$ 500	\$ (683)	\$ (183)	\$ -0-
Distribution of <i>Library Issues</i> to ARL libraries	-0-	2,500 (134)	2,500 (134)	-0-
American Library Association Chicago, IL				
Collection management institute	1,150	(900)	250	-0-
Financing online search services	2,110	(2,110)	-0-	-0-
Association of Research Libraries, Washington, D.C.				
Academic Library Program	143,500	-0-	60,000	83,500
ARL/RLG joint project on decision support systems for libraries	15,000	-0-	10,000	5,000
Collection assessment for small academic libraries	11,200	-0-	9,000	2,200
Atlanta College of Art Atlanta, GA	-0-	2,000	1,500	500
Dillard University New Orleans, LA	-0-	2,000	1,500	500
Tougaloo College Tougaloo, MS	-0-	2,000	1,500	500
Tuskegee Institute Tuskegee Institute, AL	-0-	2,000	1,500	500
Association for Asian Studies Ann Arbor, MI				
South Asia Library Workshop	500	(2,425)	(1,925)	-0-

GRANTS AND CONTRACTS

	FY 1982			
	Unpaid 6/30/81	Grants (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/82
Jovana J. Brown				
Olympia, WA				
Study of the funding of academic library research in Britain	\$ -0-	\$ 5,000	\$ 4,000	\$ 1,000
C. Donald Cook				
Toronto, Canada				
Study of forms of AACR2 catalog headings used by national libraries	-0-	15,000	10,000	5,000
Council of National Library and Information Associations				
Haverford, PA				
Support of American National Standards Committee Z39	-0-	5,000	-0-	5,000
Duke University				
Durham, NC				
Research on Byzantine bindings	-0-	7,500	5,000	2,500
Earlham College, Richmond, IN				
Periodical list for <i>Choice</i>	2,200	-0-	-0-	2,200
6th Conference on Biblio- graphic Instruction	-0-	7,600	5,900	1,700
7th Conference on Biblio- graphic Instruction	-0-	7,500	-0-	7,500
Forest Press, Albany, NY				
Investigation of the need for an Arabic edition of the Dewey Decimal Classification	6,000	-0-	3,930	2,070
International Association of School Librarianship, Kalamazoo, MI				
Program expansion	-0-	750	750	-0-
International Council on Archives, Paris, France				
Special projects	3,000	-0-	3,000	-0-
Additional projects	20,000	-0-	15,500	4,500

GRANTS AND CONTRACTS

	FY 1982			
	Unpaid 6/30/81	Grants (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/82
International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions, The Hague, Netherlands				
International Office for Universal Bibliographic Control	\$ 3,756	\$ -0-	\$ 3,756	\$ -0-
Special projects	42,000	-0-	10,000	32,000
Costs to establish IFLA/ P.R.C. liaison	1,000	-0-	1,000	-0-
Report on copyright and materials for the handicapped	-0-	5,000	4,000	1,000
International study of cataloging in publication	-0-	5,000	5,000	-0-
Review of international standard bibliographic descriptions	-0-	15,000	12,500	2,500
Travel funds for IFLA representative at inter- national congress on UAP	-0-	1,500	1,500	-0-
Lesotho Library Association Lesotho, Africa				
Workshop for training school librarians	500	(500)	-0-	-0-
Library of Congress Washington, D.C.				
Travel grant for L.C. representative at British conference on resource sharing	1,000	-0-	-0-	1,000
National Association of State Universities and Land Grant Colleges, Office for Advance- ment of Public Negro Colleges Atlanta, GA				
Status report on libraries of black public colleges	1,000	(1,000)	-0-	-0-
National Endowment for the Humanities, Washington, D.C.				
College Library Program	-0-	(932)	(932)	-0-

GRANTS AND CONTRACTS

	FY 1982			
	Unpaid 6/30/81	Grants (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/82
Plainedge Public Library				
Massapequa, NY.				
Research to determine reasons for nonuse of public libraries	\$9,750	\$ (9,750)	\$ -0-	\$ -0-
C.W. Post Center of Long Island University,				
Greenvale, NY.				
Faculty development project in information science	1,000	(1,000)	-0-	-0-
Rutherford D. Rogers				
New Haven, CT.				
Travel grant to chair IFLA Programme Management Committee	3,869	-0-	2,967 (406)	1,308
Society of American Archivists, Chicago, IL.				
Pilot project for self-study and peer review of archives	9,670	-0-	8,000	1,670
University of California Berkeley, CA.				
National shelflist measurement project	8,293	(8,293)	-0-	-0-
University of California Los Angeles, CA.				
Third edition of <i>Handbook of Data Processing for Libraries</i>	9,500	(8,617)	883	-0-
University of Kentucky Lexington, KY.				
Preparation of "Leaders in American Academic Librarianship 1925-75"	4,000	(33)	3,967	-0-
University of Michigan Ann Arbor, MI.				
Study of the relationship between bibliographic access to stored materials and faculty attitude and use	-0-	56,747	25,000	31,747

GRANTS AND CONTRACTS

	FY 1982			
	Unpaid 6/30/81	Grants (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/82
Virginia Polytechnic Institute and State University Blacksburg, VA.				
Research on use of library materials	\$ -0-	\$ 7,000	\$ 4,690	\$ 2,310
University of Wyoming Laramie, WY.				
Support of <i>Conservation Administration News</i>	2,000	(265)	1,735	-0-
Subtotals	302,498	149,097 (36,642)	220,828 (3,580)	197,705

COUNCIL-ADMINISTERED PROJECTS

	FY 1982			
	Unpaid 6/30/81	Grants (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/82
Academic Library Management				
Intern Program				
1980-81	\$ 25,899	\$ (280)	\$ 25,723 (104)	\$ -0-
1981-82	-0-	122,420 (1,023)	119,166	2,231
Bibliographic Service				
Development Program				
Association of Research Libraries, Washington, D.C.				
ARL microform project	20,000	-0-	10,000	10,000
Planning for CONSER ab- stracting and indexing coverage	-0-	2,500	2,500	-0-
Battelle Memorial Institute Columbus Laboratories Columbus, OH				
Training in the use of the BIBLINK model	11,059	(6,076)	4,983	-0-
Boston Theological Institute Cambridge, MA				
Increasing access to theologi- cal journal literature	-0-	3,431	-0-	3,431
Pauline Cochrane Fayetteville, NY				
Developing an improved entry vocabulary for Library of Congress subject headings	-0-	14,310	6,826	7,484
Council of National Library and Information Associations Haverford, PA				
Support of American National Standards Committee Z39	-0-	10,000	-0-	10,000
Dartmouth College Library Hanover, NH				
Participant in joint project to evaluate online public access catalogs	12,919	-0-	7,500	5,419
Howard Harris & Patricia Harris, Silver Spring, MD				
Position paper on an institu- tion identification code standard	666	(666)	-0-	-0-

COUNCIL-ADMINISTERED PROJECTS

	FY 1982			
	Unpaid 6/30/81	Grants (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/82
Institute for Research in Social Science, University of North Carolina Chapel Hill, NC				
Machine-readable data files cataloging manual	\$ 248	\$ (51)	\$ 197	\$ -0-
Library of Congress Washington, DC.				
Joint project for authori- ties implementation	-0-	221,998	-0-	221,998
Conversion of retrospective name authority files	63,000	(63,000)	-0-	-0-
Travel grant for L.C. repre- sentative at International Standards Organization meeting	-0-	1,100	1,100	-0-
Participant in joint project to evaluate online public access catalogs	11,351	-0-	5,000	6,351
Travel costs for the Linked Systems Project (with RLG & WLN)	20,172	-0-	9,933	10,239
J. Matthews & Associates Grass Valley, CA				
Participant in joint project to define standard data ele- ments and data collection methods for online public access catalog evaluation	2,125	-0-	2,125	-0-
Participant in joint project to evaluate online public access catalogs	99,500	-0-	38,730	60,770
Northwestern University Evanston, IL				
Development of an appli- cation level protocol	36,000	-0-	30,000	6,000
Participant in joint project to evaluate online public access catalogs	25,260	-0-	24,000	1,260
Canadian interface— application level protocol	-0-	4,500	-0-	4,500
OCLC, Dublin, OH				
Participant in joint project to evaluate online public access catalogs	-0-	164,000	150,000	14,000

COUNCIL-ADMINISTERED PROJECTS

	FY 1982			
	Unpaid 6/30/81	Grants (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/82
Participant in joint project to define standard data elements and data collection methods in online public access catalog evaluation	\$ 2,500	\$ -0-	\$ 2,500	\$ -0-
Pilot test of online public access catalog evaluation tools	-0-	16,100	16,100	-0-
Pittsburgh Regional Library Center, Pittsburgh, PA				
Serials cancellation project	24,000	-0-	15,000	9,000
Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute, Troy, NY				
Planning a thesaurus for the fields of art and architecture	3,056	-0-	3,056	-0-
The Research Libraries Group, Stanford, CA				
Joint project for authorities implementation	-0-	342,528	-0-	342,528
Toward the formation of a nationwide authority file service (joint project with WLN & LC)	124,156	-0-	107,602	16,554
Inclusion of three research libraries in preliminary work for online public access catalog project	1,892	-0-	1,892	-0-
Participant in joint project to define standard data elements and data collection methods in online public access catalog evaluation	2,850	(13)	2,837	-0-
Participant in joint project to evaluate online public access catalogs	116,614	-0-	114,000	2,614
Joint project for Standard Network Interconnection	-0-	395,000	98,750	296,250
Rutgers University New Brunswick, NJ				
Inventory of machine readable texts in the humanities	-0-	14,166	-0-	14,166

COUNCIL-ADMINISTERED PROJECTS

FY 1982

	Unpaid 6/30/81	Grants (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/82
Stanford University Libraries				
Stanford, CA				
Participant in joint project to evaluate online public access catalogs	\$ 20,960	\$ (1,000)	\$ 18,000	\$ 1,960
University of California				
Berkeley, CA				
Participant in joint project to define standard data elements and data collection methods in online public access catalog evaluation	550	(692)	(142)	-0-
Participant in joint project to evaluate online public access catalogs	22,000	-0-	21,000	1,000
Analysis of data collected in the online catalog evaluation project	113,000	-0-	60,000	53,000
University of Illinois				
Urbana, IL				
Analysis of MARC data base statistics	15,570	-0-	-0-	15,570
University of Michigan				
Ann Arbor, MI				
A system for creating and maintaining bibliographies	-0-	7,500	1,000	6,500
University of Toronto Library				
Automation Systems				
Toronto, Canada				
Online public access catalog evaluation	-0-	20,160 (20,160)	-0-	-0-
Washington Library Network				
Olympia, WA				
Toward the formation of a nationwide authority file service (joint project with RLG & LC) phase 1	92,250	(31,936)	45,314	15,000
Toward the formation of a nationwide authority file service (joint project with RLG & LC) phase 2	182,197	-0-	136,648	45,549
Joint project for authorities implementation	-0-	323,347	-0-	323,347

COUNCIL-ADMINISTERED PROJECTS

	FY 1982			
	Unpaid 6/30/81	Grants (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/82
Joint project for Standard Network Interconnection	\$ -0-	\$ 330,000	\$ 82,500	\$ 247,500
Total Bibliographic Service Development Program	1,023,895	1,870,640 (123,594)	1,019,093 (142)	1,751,990
Fellowship Program	5,820	(1,930)	3,890	-0-
Health Sciences Library Management Intern Program 1980-81	4,822	(2,803)	2,019	-0-
Professional Education and Training for Research Librar- ianship (PETREL)				
Lauren Kelly Los Angeles, CA.				
Senior fellows program	-0-	4,500	-0-	4,500
University of California Los Angeles, CA.				
Senior fellows program				
1982-83	125,000	(4,500)	-0-	120,500
1983-85	-0-	127,000	-0-	127,000
Frontiers conference	90,000	-0-	50,000	40,000
University of Chicago Chicago, IL.				
Special program of advanced study in library management	235,000	-0-	-0-	235,000
University of Michigan Ann Arbor, MI.				
Basic professional education for research librarianship	273,000	-0-	40,000	233,000
Total PETREL	723,000	131,500 (4,500)	90,000	760,000
Travel assistance				
H.D.L. Vervliet, University of Antwerp, Belgium				
Study trip to U.S. research libraries	2,000	-0-	2,000	-0-

COUNCIL-ADMINISTERED PROJECTS

	FY 1982			
	Unpaid 6/30/81	Grants (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/82
Total CLR-administered projects	\$ 1,785,436	\$ 2,124,560 (134,130)	\$ 1,261,891 (246)	\$ 2,514,221
Subtotals page 46	302,498	149,097 (36,642)	220,828 (3,580)	197,705
TOTALS	<u>\$ 2,087,934</u>	<u>\$ 2,273,657</u> (170,772)	<u>\$1,482,719</u> (3,826)	<u>\$ 2,711,926</u>

Opinion of Independent Accountant

August 6, 1982

To the Board of Directors of
Council on Library Resources, Inc.

We have examined the balance sheet of the Council on Library Resources, Inc. as of June 30, 1982 and 1981, and the related statements of revenues, expenses and changes in fund balances, and of changes in cash and short-term investments for the years then ended. Our examinations were made in accordance with generally accepted auditing standards and accordingly included such tests of the accounting records and such other auditing procedures as we considered necessary in the circumstances.

In our opinion, the financial statements examined by us present fairly the financial position of the Council on Library Resources, Inc. at June 30, 1982 and 1981, and the results of its operations and the changes in its cash and short-term investments for the years then ended, in conformity with generally accepted accounting principles consistently applied.

Our examinations were made primarily for the purpose of forming our opinion on the financial statements, taken as a whole. We also examined the supplementary statement of revenues, expenses and changes in fund balances, by similar procedures. In our opinion, this supplementary information is stated fairly in all material respects in relation to the financial statements, taken as a whole. Although not essential for a fair presentation of financial position, results of operations and changes in cash and short-term investments, this information is submitted as additional data.

Price Waterhouse
Washington, D.C.

Balance Sheet

	JUNE 30	
	<u>1982</u>	<u>1981</u>
ASSETS		
Cash and short-term investments	\$2,751,266	\$2,560,919
Grants receivable (Note 2)	3,266,411	4,532,687
Prepaid expenses and deposits	<u>5,661</u>	<u>27,235</u>
Total assets	<u><u>\$6,023,338</u></u>	<u><u>\$7,120,841</u></u>
 LIABILITIES AND FUND BALANCE		
Deferred income (Note 2)	\$1,777,908	\$3,770,961
Grants and contracts payable	2,711,926	2,087,934
Accounts payable and accrued employee benefits	86,800	42,472
Federal excise taxes payable	<u>6,638</u>	<u>5,063</u>
Total liabilities	<u><u>4,583,272</u></u>	<u><u>5,906,430</u></u>
Unrestricted fund balance		
Appropriated	681,443	146,897
Unappropriated	<u>758,623</u>	<u>1,067,514</u>
Total fund balance	<u><u>1,440,066</u></u>	<u><u>1,214,411</u></u>
Total liabilities and fund balance	<u><u>\$6,023,338</u></u>	<u><u>\$7,120,841</u></u>

Statement of Revenues, Expenses and Changes in Fund Balance

FOR THE YEARS ENDED JUNE 30, 1982 AND 1981

	Unrestricted	Restricted	Total
Fund balance, June 30, 1980	\$ <u>800,629</u>		\$ <u>800,629</u>
Revenues (Note 2)			
Grants and contracts	700,000	\$2,081,519	2,781,519
Investment income	252,897		252,897
Royalty income	<u>268</u>		<u>268</u>
Total revenues	<u>953,165</u>	<u>2,081,519</u>	<u>3,034,684</u>
Expenses (Note 2)			
Program services	265,713	2,081,519	2,347,232
Administrative services	<u>273,670</u>		<u>273,670</u>
Total expenses	<u>539,383</u>	<u>2,081,519</u>	<u>2,620,902</u>
Excess of revenues over expenses	<u>413,782</u>		<u>413,782</u>
Fund balance, June 30, 1981	<u>1,214,411</u>		<u>1,214,411</u>
Revenues (Note 2)			
Grants and contracts	700,000	2,113,806	2,813,806
Investment income	330,510		330,510
Royalty income	<u>1,401</u>		<u>1,401</u>
Total revenues	<u>1,031,911</u>	<u>2,113,806</u>	<u>3,145,717</u>
Expenses (Note 2)			
Program services	482,577	2,113,806	2,596,383
Administrative services	<u>323,679</u>		<u>323,679</u>
Total expenses	<u>806,256</u>	<u>2,113,806</u>	<u>2,920,062</u>
Excess of revenues over expenses	<u>225,655</u>		<u>225,655</u>
Fund balance, June 30, 1982	<u>\$1,440,066</u>	\$ <u> </u>	<u>\$1,440,066</u>

Statement of Changes in Cash and Short-term Investments

FOR THE YEARS ENDED JUNE 30, 1982 AND 1981

	<u>1982</u>	<u>1981</u>
Sources of cash and short-term investments		
Excess of revenues over expenses	\$ 225,655	\$ 413,782
Increase in grants and contracts payable	623,992	936,801
Decrease in grants receivable	<u>1,266,276</u>	<u>1,466,571</u>
	<u>2,115,923</u>	<u>2,817,154</u>
Uses of cash and short-term investments		
Decrease in deferred income	1,993,053	2,216,519
(Increase) decrease in federal excise taxes, accounts payable and accrued employee benefits	(45,903)	2,664
(Decrease) increase in prepaid expenses and deposits	<u>(21,574)</u>	<u>18,473</u>
	<u>1,925,576</u>	<u>2,237,656</u>
Increase in cash and short-term investments for the year	190,347	579,498
Cash and short-term investments, beginning of year	<u>2,560,919</u>	<u>1,981,421</u>
Cash and short-term investments, end of year	<u>\$2,751,266</u>	<u>\$2,560,919</u>

Notes to Financial Statements

JUNE 30, 1982 AND 1981

1. Organization

The Council on Library Resources, Inc. (Council) is a non-profit organization incorporated under the laws of the District of Columbia in 1956 for the purpose of promoting library research. The Council's operations are financed primarily through unrestricted general support grants from The Ford Foundation and The Andrew W. Mellon Foundation and through several restricted grants and contracts from private foundations and other sources. The Council conducts its work through directly administered projects as well as grants to and contracts with other organizations or individuals.

The Council is a private operating foundation and is exempt from Federal income tax under Internal Revenue Code section 501(c)(3). It is, however, subject to a 2% excise tax on investment and royalty income under the provisions of the Revenue Act of 1978.

2. Summary of Significant Accounting Policies

The Council's financial statements are prepared on an accrual basis. Grants are recorded as receivable at such time as the Council is notified that it has been awarded the funds. Unrestricted grant revenue is recognized in accordance with the budgeted annual payments specified by the grantors. Interest and royalty income are recognized as unrestricted grant revenue. Restricted grant revenue is recognized to the extent of the related expenses. Grant and contract expenses are recorded when the recipients are notified that they are to receive the funds. All unrecognized grant revenue is recorded as deferred income.

The costs of office furniture and equipment are consistently charged to expense when incurred. The Council does not consider such expenditures to be sufficiently material to warrant capitalization and depreciation.

3. Retirement Plan

Employees are eligible for participation in the Council's retirement annuity program, which is administered through the TIAA/CREF insurance companies. Individual contracts issued under the plan provide for full and immediate vesting of both the Council's and employees' contributions. The Council's contribution amounted to \$56,000 and \$46,000 for fiscal year 1982 and 1981, respectively.

4. Commitments

The Council entered into a lease agreement for office space expiring in 1987 which may be cancelled after the expiration of three years, with one year notice. The minimum future rentals as of June 30, 1982 are \$132,180 annually for fiscal years 1983 and 1984 and \$121,165 for fiscal year 1985.

SUPPLEMENTARY STATEMENT OF REVENUES, EXPENSES AND CHANGES IN FUND BALANCE

FOR THE YEARS ENDED JUNE 30, 1982 AND 1981

	Unrestricted				
	Ford Foundation	Mellon Foundation	Other	Total Unrestricted	Bibliographic Service Development Program (Note 2)
Revenues					
Grants and Contracts	\$500,000	\$200,000		\$ 700,000	\$1,900,078
Investment income			\$330,510	330,510	
Royalty income			1,401	1,401	
Total revenues	500,000	200,000	331,911	1,031,911	1,900,078
Expenses (Note 1)					
Program services					
Grants and contracts	175,872	68,395		244,267	1,870,640
Council-administered projects	9,536	3,708		13,244	153,032
Less adjustments resulting from excess allocations of grants and contracts	(22,146)	(8,612)	(8,617)	(39,375)	(123,594)
Compensation and employee benefits	161,928	62,972		224,900	
Professional fees	3,682	1,432		5,114	
Travel and meetings	5,072	1,973		7,045	
Other expenses	10,095	3,926	13,361	27,382	
	344,039	133,794	4,744	482,577	1,900,078
Administrative services					
Compensation and employee benefits	107,150	41,669		148,819	
Travel and meetings	19,711	7,666		27,377	
Professional fees	7,621	2,964		10,585	
Rent	45,094	17,537		62,631	
Equipment rental and furniture	10,897	4,238		15,135	
Printing	6,929	2,695		9,624	
Office and other expenses	30,866	12,004	6,638	49,508	
	228,268	88,773	6,638	323,679	
Total expenses	572,307	222,567	11,382	806,256	1,900,078
Excess (deficit) of revenues over expenses	(72,307)	(22,567)	320,529	225,655	
Fund balance, beginning of year	481,956	185,897	546,558	1,214,411	
Fund balance, end of year	\$409,649	\$163,330	\$867,087	\$1,440,066	\$

Restricted

CLR Review (Note 3)	Health Sciences Management Intern Program (Note 4)	International Programs (Note 5)	Project on Research Libraries (Note 6)	Professional Education and Training for Research Librarianship (Note 7)	Total Restricted	Total 1982	Total 1981
\$11,784	\$(2,526)	\$30,891	\$5,849	\$167,730	\$2,113,806	\$2,813,806	\$2,781,519
						330,510	252,897
						1,401	268
<u>11,784</u>	<u>(2,526)</u>	<u>30,891</u>	<u>5,849</u>	<u>167,730</u>	<u>2,113,806</u>	<u>3,145,717</u>	<u>3,034,684</u>
		27,250		131,500	2,029,390	2,273,657	1,978,752
11,784	277	4,141	5,849	40,730	215,813	229,057	211,563
	(2,803)	(500)		(4,500)	(131,397)	(170,772)	(54,836)
						224,900	195,301
						5,114	7,567
						7,045	8,004
						27,382	881
<u>11,784</u>	<u>(2,526)</u>	<u>30,891</u>	<u>5,849</u>	<u>167,730</u>	<u>2,113,806</u>	<u>2,596,383</u>	<u>2,347,232</u>
						148,819	134,924
						27,377	26,938
						10,585	14,060
						62,631	49,249
						15,135	3,242
						9,624	10,222
						49,508	35,035
						<u>323,679</u>	<u>273,670</u>
<u>11,784</u>	<u>(2,526)</u>	<u>30,891</u>	<u>5,849</u>	<u>167,730</u>	<u>2,113,806</u>	<u>2,920,062</u>	<u>2,620,902</u>
						225,655	413,782
						1,214,411	800,629
<u>\$</u>	<u>\$</u>	<u>\$</u>	<u>\$</u>	<u>\$</u>	<u>\$</u>	<u>\$1,440,066</u>	<u>\$1,214,411</u>

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC.

Notes to Supplementary Statement of Revenues, Expenses and Changes in Fund Balance

FOR THE YEARS ENDED JUNE 30, 1982 AND 1981

1. Allocation of Expenses

Under the terms of the Ford and Mellon Foundations' unrestricted general support grants, the Council must account for expenditures of these funds on an individual basis. The Council allocates these expenses between the Ford and Mellon grants based upon the ratio of the sums of the respective fund balances at the beginning of the year and current year's revenue. Unrestricted expenses related to investment and royalty income are excluded from the Ford and Mellon allocation process.

2. Bibliographic Service Development Program

The Council had been awarded restricted grants totaling \$4,700,000 as of June 30, 1981 and received an increase to \$5,200,000 in 1982. The funding for this program was received from the Carnegie Corporation of New York, The Commonwealth Fund, The Ford Foundation, The William and Flora Hewlett Foundation, The Lilly Endowment, Inc., The Andrew W. Mellon Foundation, the National Endowment for the Humanities and the Alfred P. Sloan Foundation. The purpose of these grants is to fund a five-year research and development project, ending in fiscal year 1985, to assist in establishing primary components of a national bibliographic system.

3. CLR Review

The Council received a restricted grant from The Ford Foundation in 1981 to conduct a review of past and present Council on Library Resources (CLR) functions and to consider its future mission.

4. Health Science Management Intern Program

Under a three-year contract with the National Library of Medicine, which ended in fiscal year 1982, the Council administered an internship program for mid-career health sciences librarians.

5. International Programs

At June 30, 1981, the Council had been awarded two restricted grants totaling \$200,000 from the Exxon Education Foundation for general support of the Council's international activities. An additional \$100,000 grant was awarded in fiscal year 1982.

6. Project on Research Libraries

The Carnegie Corporation, The Andrew W. Mellon Foundation, and the National Endowment for the Humanities have awarded funds to the Council and the Association of American Universities for a joint project to address problems of research libraries.

7. Professional Education and Training for Research Librarianship

The Council has been awarded two restricted grants totaling \$1,100,000 from the Carnegie Corporation of New York and The Andrew W. Mellon Foundation to partially fund a new program of professional education and training for research librarians. Additional funding is being sought for this program.

8. Management Programs

The Council also has available the balance of restricted funds from the Carnegie Corporation for programs to improve the management of research libraries.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC.

Grant Application Procedures

Initial inquiries regarding possible project support should be in the form of a letter, which should include the following information:

1. Name and address of requesting individual or organization, and the name of the proposed principal investigator.
2. Type of institution.
3. Tax status.
4. A clear statement of the aims of the project and its significance, including details of the general approach and specific research methods to be used.
5. Amount of request and proposed budget for the project.
6. Period to be covered by the project.

With this information, each proposed project can be evaluated in terms of how it fits the Council's current program priorities. If a project is judged to be of possible interest, advice will be offered as to proposal preparation, and additional information may be requested. There are no deadlines for general grant applications.

All inquiries should be addressed to: Warren J. Haas, President, Council on Library Resources, Inc., 1785 Massachusetts Ave., N.W., Washington, D.C. 20036.

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